

SUSTAINABLE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT TO STRENGTHEN LOCAL ECONOMIES USING THE TOURIST TRAIL APPROACH: EVALUATE AND MEASURE THE SUCCESS OF HERITAGE WALKS IN A FEW HISTORICAL CITIES ACROSS INDIA

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ABSTRACT:

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INTRODUCTION:

Tourism has a significant role as a key engine of economic growth in the contemporary era. The tourism industry has witnessed a shift from traditional historical tourism to a new focus on "experiences" and in-destination activities, presenting vast financial opportunities. Tourism is dependent upon the host community or local community. It is of utmost importance to demonstrate respect and comprehension towards the values, principles, and sentiments held by the community, and to collaborate effectively with them. The amalgamation of tourism and history has given rise to new career trajectories within this industry.

Several cities in India depend on some form of tourism, either complementing or enabling their economies to develop and sustain. The preservation of the heritage and culture of such destinations depends on sustainable tourism. Heritage walks are an effective strategy to honour and preserve a region's heritage as well as promote cultural appreciation and understanding among locals and tourists. They contribute to improving the tourism industry, and educational opportunities, and preserving historical artefacts for future generations. They foster connections between participants and the local community to cultivate a sense of shared ownership and pride in preserving cultural heritage.

Mysore is rich in heritage and culture encompassing a total of over 201 buildings and locations of historical and cultural significance. The Heritage Commissioners Office, Mysore City Corporation, and Tourism Department have collectively undertaken the responsibility of promoting

awareness and appreciation of the heritage and culture of Mysore City. This initiative involves active engagement with various stakeholders in the community. The scholars engage in a discussion regarding the various measures implemented and the heritage walk devised by the committee. The researchers propose that by conducting a SWOT analysis of the heritage walk and examining the actions implemented by the committee, policies can be recommended to enhance awareness of heritage and culture. These policies would involve restructuring the heritage walks to include sites related to the freedom movement, ecological and biological sites, street plays, children's books, freedom walks, and Tonga tours.(Shankar, 2013)

Sustainable tourism is an approach to travel that seeks to reduce the industry's negative effects on local environments, communities, and ecosystems while maximizing positive ones. The primary objective of sustainable tourism is to ensure that tourism activities are carried out in a manner that preserves the ecological and cultural integrity of the destination, promotes socioeconomic development, and benefits both visitors and host communities.

When designed and implemented with a focus on sustainability, the Tourist Trail Approach helps achieve a balance between tourism promotion and environmental and cultural preservation. It seeks to create enriching and responsible travel experiences for visitors, while also benefiting local communities and preserving the natural and cultural heritage of the destination for future

generations.

A tourist trail approach, also known as a tourist route or travel route, is a preplanned itinerary or path that connects multiple tourist attractions, monuments, or points of interest within a given destination. Its purpose is to enhance travellers' travels as a whole by guiding them through a logical and well-organized sequence of attractions or experiences. The objective of a tourist trail is to enhance the travel experience by providing a well-structured and rewarding journey through a destination's main attractions and experiences. It offers tourists a thorough and immersive method to explore a location, thereby making their trip more enjoyable and memorable.

As part of the tourist trail strategy, heritage walks are frequently community-led or involve direct collaboration with local stakeholders. These initiatives cultivate community pride and participation in the preservation of cultural heritage. These activities benefit local artisans, guides, and businesses, resulting in greater cultural sustainability.

Walking is a fantastic method to learn about history, including monuments, rituals and festivals. This makes individuals appreciate heritage materials and desire the government to safeguard and preserve them better. To showcase their culture, some locals manage and improve cultural relics.

Recent growth in the prevalence of heritage walks has resulted in a paucity of research in the field, particularly concerning the relationship between heritage walks and heritage education. This is particularly accurate for India.

This study looks at how heritage walks support and promote inclusive learning about heritage to fill this gap in academic research, make a contribution to the field of heritage tourism and protection and contribute towards strengthening local economies.

HERITAGE:

Limited research studies and scholarly papers have been conducted on the subject of heritage walks in urban areas of India.

Historical places have historically attracted both local and foreign tourists. The preservation of history and the maintenance of museum quality and management play a crucial role in promoting tourism in several historical and cultural destinations. Cultural tourism emphasizes the significance of heritage monuments. Heritage sites can be regarded as tangible manifestations or creations of historical events or processes, and their connection to the past is frequently reinterpreted or recontextualized. The cultural representations of these monuments have the potential to provide both instructional and entertaining experiences. The presence of these valuable artefacts and cultural legacies contributes to the overall richness of a region, hence attracting a significant number of tourists with a keen interest in cultural exploration. Cultural tourism is currently seeing rapid growth, but, its full

potential remains unexplored.

Heritage is not limited to buildings. Heritage, both cultural and natural, tangible and intangible, is an evolving resource. It aids individuals in remembering who they are and where they came from, and it is crucial to attaining sustainable growth. It increases social well-being, makes regions more attractive and innovative, and enhances the tourism industry's long-term benefits. It also makes it simpler for individuals to get along with one another. We must undertake the responsibility of protecting this fragile, non-renewable resource for future generations. (Sophia Labadi, 2021)

Recently, the researchers examined how "participatory governance of cultural heritage," or "PGCH" for short, is becoming increasingly central to the debate in Europe regarding how to manage cultural heritage policy. They apply a multi-actor, commons-based administration model to this subject, which is a novel perspective. Adopting a "commons-oriented" approach in the PGCH entails implementing a "governance" paradigm that seeks to ensure the resource's long-term social and economic health. In each instance, the various types of partnerships formed had distinct effects on the operation of the PGCH. If, on the one hand, the role of public actors is still crucial to ensure that these models of self-governance remain in place over time, then, on the other hand, the community that is actively involved in the management of the resource should also be responsible and act collectively to ensure that the intervention lasts. Additionally, legal instruments that were created for this purpose or already exist can facilitate collaboration. Communities are now viewed as potential and powerful allies of public organizations in the design and implementation of social services and/or goods, as well as the management of local cultural assets. This is especially true when considering the significance of cultural heritage to society. (Christian Iaione, 2022)

HERITAGE WALKS:

In his study in 2010, Joby Thomas found that heritage walks promote sustainable tourism and direct visitors to historically wealthy but unexplored regions. Although many cities offer Heritage excursions in some form or another, the vast majority of tourists have never participated in one. It was discovered that the walks could increase tourism among residents by helping them discover their origins and leading to a rise in local pride. (Thomas, 2010)

Using management theories in the heritage management research domain, the researchers in 2016 explored the value network in heritage walk organizations for creating shared value - a form of value described by Porter and Kramer as placing social and community requirements ahead of profit. Their paper investigates the value network in three heritage excursions organized by three organizations in the western Indian city of Ahmedabad. These walks include architecture, communities, craftsmanship, cuisine, and other aspects of living and non-living heritage. (Saiyed, 2016)

Although their function and utility as applied tourism products have been analyzed, trails and routes continue to be under-theorized in the academic literature. In 2017, Nicola MacLeod wrote an article about the role of trails in the social and cultural construction of space. This piece helps to fill this gap. In particular, the potential role of trails in making themed, static spaces is looked at, and the term "museumization" is used to show how trails can be used to change the way spaces are set up within certain cultural frames that may not include local identity but are still enjoyed by the unquestioning visitor. Using such contemporary approaches, this article argues for the efficacy of trails as flexible, interpretive tools that can tell many different kinds of stories and get people to interact more with the places they visit. (MacLeod, 2017)

In a recent study, the researchers demonstrated heritage walks play an important function beyond imparting historical and cultural knowledge. They play a crucial role in fostering a greater appreciation for heritage and conservation. (Ekta Chauhan, 2021)

In a book chapter, Rodney Harrison provides an outstanding illustration of how to design contemporary heritage walks. Since 2002, Jay Brown, a former Brixton inhabitant with extensive ties to the neighbourhood and a member of the British African Caribbean community, has led Brixton Walking Tours. She was inspired by community-based tourism ventures in Harlem, the United States of America, and South America that are operated by locals and provide tourists with a secure means of gaining a different perspective on a different culture. The Brixton Walking Tour led by Jay Brown is an example of a commonplace heritage practice: the walking tour. However, neither the nature nor the location of this walk is typical. Most people may think of the Houses of Parliament, Big Ben, Madame Tussaud's, and the Tower of London when they consider the heritage of London. Jay's walking tour is distinctive in that it exposes tourists to a section of south London that they might not otherwise visit due to dread or invisibility. (Harrison, 2012)

HERITAGE WALKS IN INDIA:

Heritage walks encompass the connection and interpretation of specific locations that hold historical and cultural importance, resulting in a unified and thematically organized exploration of physical space. The activity of urban conservation plays a crucial role in shaping the history and character of a city through fostering community engagement and interest. (Shah, 2021)

While Heritage walks are popular in European and American cities, the trend is yet to gain traction across the cities in India. However, it is worth noting that Delhi and Mumbai have emerged as frontrunners in promoting Heritage Walks among both tourists and visitors. Numerous private operators have designed a diverse array of guided tours spanning various areas of the cities, providing participants with a comprehensive account of the historical and cultural aspects associated with these excursions. In addition to Delhi and Mumbai, several other

cities in India have initiated the organization of heritage walks, showcasing their rich historical and cultural significance.

The walks offered are centred around certain themes, allowing participants to engage in local experience exploration within a leisurely timeframe often spanning 2 to 3 hours. Storytelling has long been recognized as a powerful means of establishing a profound impact and fostering a sense of connection with various locations throughout history. The utilization of narratives during heritage walks has a significant impact, fostering an emotional bond that motivates communities, cultures, and environments to actively engage in the sharing of their historical experiences. The genre of heritage walks has evolved into a comprehensive ecosystem of tourism products, resulting in the expansion of local employment opportunities and economic development.

According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), India ranks in the top ten countries renowned for its heritage sites. Rajasthan is renowned for its rich cultural heritage and impressive fortifications. The authors examine the significance of Heritage walks as a tourism offering in terms of their potential to stimulate economic growth and generate employment possibilities for local communities. Rajasthan's rich cultural traditions and abundance of heritage monuments render it a highly significant destination for tourism. (Mathur, 2022)

Some notable walks in India are Delhi Heritage Walks, Midnight Calcutta Walks, Journeys Through India, Craft Walks in Kashmir and Street Art Walks. The business model varies by speciality, but the participants can reserve walk-time sessions on various websites. They can also call portal booking lines to book appointments. Two to three hours are typical for walks.

The registration fees range from INR 500 to 3,000 for tourists. Services supplied during walks affect the price model. Art Walks Mumbai, held monthly, costs INR 600 per person for 2.5 hours. Meanwhile, The Bookworming Tour, Delhi and Mumbai charges INR 3,500 per person, including snacks, and INR 800-1,000 per person for their group tour.

THE MOST POPULAR HERITAGE WALKS OF INDIA ARE:

- The Ahmedabad City Walk, Ahmedabad
- The Mysore City Walk, Mysore
- The Panjim Walk, Goa
- Vintage Heritage Walk, Jaipur
- The Heritage Walk, Jodhpur
- The Worli Walk & The Dadar Walk, Mumbai
- Delwara Heritage Walk, Delwara
- The Humayun's Tomb Walk & The Old City Walk, Delhi

ATTRIBUTES OF TOURISM RELATED TO HERITAGE & CULTURE:

Heritage manifests itself through various elements, such as architectural structures, natural landscapes, culinary traditions, gardens, historical monuments, artistic expressions, craftsmanship, and the overall embodiment of a certain way of life.

Published in 2009, the paper by Rebecca Sims argues that local cuisine can play a significant role in sustainable tourism because it appeals to visitors' desire for authenticity during their vacation. Using evidence from qualitative interviews with tourists and food producers, this paper examines how local foods are conceptualized as "authentic" products that represent the destination's culture and location. (Sims, 2009)

The researchers regard the FARO convention as a framework for examining heritage walks as a means of fostering social, economic, and cultural benefits within local communities. The report additionally proposes a novel approach to the strategic organization of heritage walks. The efficacy of a novel approach referred to as the study circle, is being examined in order to assess its impact on enhancing the educational experience by fostering active engagement among participants during historical walks, with the aim of cultivating cultural knowledge. The study circle exhibited several key attributes, including an informal atmosphere, self-directed learning, experiential engagement, and the active participation of all members in information sharing, rather than solely relying on the mentor's input. The implementation of the study circle approach has been identified as a significant factor in enhancing the overall quality of heritage walks. (Tasso, 2017)

The researchers note in their 2018 publication that significant changes in the mode of city sightseeing have become apparent in recent years. Tourists are forsaking historic city centres for less typical tourist destinations. In these regions, alternative forms of urban tourism, known as off-the-beaten-path tourism, are developing. This is notably true of old cities in Europe, particularly capital cities and large cities such as Krakow, one of Poland's largest and often referred to as its cultural capital. In their case study, they illustrate the issue in the context of two districts, namely Nowa Huta and Podgórze. In both districts, changes to the city's tourist model can be observed. This is because tourists now visit cities for a variety of reasons and utilize their free time in a variety of ways. Tourism in the city must be managed according to the principles of sustainable development, and the cultural and historical authenticity of sites and buildings must be preserved for this process to be successful. (Pawłowska, 2018)

Lachlan B. Barber devised a typology of heritage trails and tours in 2019 to determine how they are positioned in the local tourism economy and context. They discuss three important issues: how tours and trails develop, how they interact with official and unofficial heritage sites, and how

they refer to urban issues, such as state-led urban renewal and redevelopment. (Barber, 2019)

While researching rural tourism and Eco-museums in the context of Italian rural communities, the researchers delve into the concept of "heritagization." They investigate the intricate set of processes and dynamics that transform a cultural asset or a traditional practice into a legacy, thereby creating and recreating cultural and historical meanings, a sense of belonging, and local or trans-local identities. Without a strong sense of community and a fully shared and participatory agenda, it is impossible to accomplish the desired synergy between responsibility and sustainability, the authors conclude. This synergy would enable the revitalization of local production practices and non-episodic actions to enhance the tourism and cultural value of local territories. However, this synergy cannot be achieved in the absence of a strong sense of community. (Angelo Belliggiano, 2021)

CHALLENGES:

In their paper, Dr Raja and Dr Raghu discuss the greatest challenge of sustainable tourism. In the past six decades, tourism has become one of the world's most influential and remarkable socioeconomic phenomena. Now, more people can travel. Tourism has evolved from an elite activity relished by the upper classes to a popular pastime enjoyed regularly by the masses. Sustainable tourism development is founded on the theory of development, specifically sustainable development. Within thirty years, the concept of development has evolved from a process or condition defined by strict economic criteria to a continuous, global process of human development guided by the principles of self-reliance; while economic growth remains a cornerstone, it also encompasses social, political, and cultural elements. This is not surprising given the extensive research on this topic and the absence of a distinct definition.

Therefore, sustainable tourism development is criticized for being overly general and open to interpretation. This may constitute a virtue. Those who disagree with the imposed definition may feel marginalized. Similar to sustainable development, sustainable tourism development is circumstantial, making it difficult to define. Since it is a destination-specific term, it may be preferable to describe it on a case-by-case basis to accommodate a diversity of situations and establish appropriate growth objectives. (Dr. P. Raja, 2020)

A case study highlights Gold Coast, Australia's urban heritage walks. The Gold Coast has no history or culture. Heritage walks help rebrand the city. Based on observational fieldwork and interviews in 2020 by Zelmarie Cantillon, the paper analyzes the walk's dominant narratives of history and urban identity and how they are experienced and understood in the modern materiality of lived space. The study underlines the city's ongoing development-preservation issues due to the lack of explanatory signs and physical history. (Cantillon, 2020)

David Lampert, in his multi-country study of a new

approach towards heritage tourism, notes a pertinent issue. Undoubtedly, there are countries with a greater variety of museums, heritage pathways of diverse ethnicities, and ethnic communities that promote their heritage openly. There may be robust local intellectual and environmental traditions. The recognition of the political liberties of communities may increase. And there may be more leisure opportunities. Where national and local community sovereignty is greater, there is a greater emphasis on heritage. Even there, however, cultures are assimilating and heritage is in danger. Numerous presentations are neither particularly challenging nor profound.(Lempert, 2020)

In their extensive, case-based policy guidance report, the authors discuss the various sustainable development goals and align them with the preservation of heritage. The Policy Guidance document is intended to increase people's awareness of the problems and opportunities associated with the link between heritage and sustainability and to demonstrate how to maximize those opportunities. Adapting the Goals to regional and local contexts and clarifying 'localizing' through active engagement with localities at the citizen and local decision-making level.(Christian Iaione, 2022)

REVIEW OF A FEW HERITAGE WALKS:

Starting in the early 2000s, the purpose of the heritage walk was to showcase the unique culture and way of life of the walled city. From casually walking certain landmarks and areas of the old city and narrating related stories, the heritage walk became more organised with thematic storytelling, visiting its cultural roots, the heritage site and buildings. Providing a context to the city and its several landmarks, heritage walks have grown immensely popular over the last 10-12 years. The walks are peppered with folklore, anecdotes and local interaction and experiences. Lasting for nearly three hours, the walk introduces several local food items and handicrafts to the participants. Taking

a walk in a city with an expert guide is an immersive experience for visitors and locals alike. The locals experience the city in a way they never have while the visitors tend to develop an emotional and intellectual relationship with the destination.

Heritage walks serve as a significant mechanism for fostering understanding and appreciation of the local heritage. It facilitates the establishment of a connection between the local communities and the rich heritage and cultural aspects of a particular location. Heritage walks serve as a means to save heritage places that face the threat of disappearance due to the increasing process of urbanization. The study examines the heritage walk organized by the Delhi Metro Rail Corporation (DMRC) in Delhi, specifically focusing on the route from HUDA metro station to Chandni Chowk Metro Station. The researcher's conclusion suggests that heritage walks had the potential to serve not just as an educational instrument, but also as a viable avenue for the tourism industry to capitalize on. The implementation of this initiative enhances employment prospects within the immediate vicinity, while concurrently fostering a sense of consciousness and linkage between the local cultural heritage and historical context and the broader societal fabric.(Kulshrestha, 2019)

Udaipur is well recognized as a prominent tourist destination in the state of Rajasthan, attracting a significant influx of both domestic and foreign visitors who are drawn to the city's captivating aesthetics and rich cultural legacy. A comprehensive analysis has been conducted on the diverse heritage walks that are arranged in Udaipur. Based on the discourse with the stakeholders, it is evident that the heritage walk has the potential to emerge as a significant tourism offering, hence generating employment prospects for the indigenous populace, among other notable aspects.(Ms. Bhumika Ranawat, 2019)

S. No.	City	Research Methodology	Year	Findings	Issues faced	Impact on Local Economies
1	Jodhpur	In-person Interview	2023	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. An immersive walk through the old city. 2. Narration of history and folklore. 3. Local interactions 4. Provide an insight into the way of life of the locals. 5. Introduction to various food specialities 6. Introduction to local arts and crafts 	The safety and security of the participants is the main concern. Lack of cleanliness in the areas covered by the walks. Stray animals sometimes create a ruckus.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promotion and sale of handicrafts. 2. The food stall and shop owners earn from the sales of their food and beverage items. 3. The locals have started selling the local experience to the participants by inviting them participants to spend some time on the blue terraces with tea and coffee.

2	Udaipur	Review of relevant literature	2019	<p>1. Complete awareness about heritage walks in Udaipur by all the stakeholders of heritage walks</p> <p>2. Maximum respondents felt that Udaipur is a suitable place to conduct heritage walks</p> <p>3. Maximum respondents felt that heritage walk can become a major tool for tourism</p> <p>4. Maximum respondents felt that heritage walk helps in generation of employment opportunities for local communities</p> <p>5. Heritage walk ensures longer stay by tourists in Udaipur</p> <p>6. Maximum people felt that Udaipur has the required resources to conduct heritage walks</p> <p>7. Government sponsored heritage walks attract more tourist and government takes initiatives to promote heritage walks</p> <p>8. People feel that heritage walks should be organized more often and can be promoted more via social media, hotels and travel agencies, newspapers, word of mouth</p>	<p>Heritage walks are not promoted at the scale at which it should.</p> <p>People felt there is lack of information about the heritage walks and hence there is little participation by the tourists in such walks.</p> <p>Some people also felt that there is lack of proper infrastructure to support heritage walks.</p> <p>Proper conservation of ancient heritage sites is a primary want of the people. Apart from the same, cleanliness in certain parts of the cities impact heritage walks in a negative manner.</p>
3.	Jaipur	Review of relevant literature			
4.	Mysore	Review of relevant literature			

CONCLUSION:

More research is needed to determine the lifespan of an inclusive approach. Regular stakeholder participation may reveal new social and institutional behaviour elements. As time between an organization and its stakeholders grows, its past risks being disregarded, forgotten, or lost. However, leaders, institutions, and community members may need ongoing assistance and advice to stay engaged. History and heritage are irreplaceable. Local communities require concern to feel responsible. Community involvement should attract more individuals and foster socially and morally responsible cultural heritage preservers. (Billore, 2021)

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